

PRIVATE SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA AND IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA – A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

Private security has become an indispensable component of national security systems in modern societies: from protecting people and property to safeguarding critical infrastructure, preventing crime, and participating in emergencies. Its regulation serves a dual purpose: to ensure the effective provision of services while safeguarding public interests, particularly when private security activities may affect citizens' fundamental rights and freedoms.

The aim of the paper is to examine the legal and institutional frameworks governing private security in the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of North Macedonia. A comparative legal-analytical approach was applied, combining a review of national laws and regulations, supported by relevant literature on private security, public-private interactions, and regulatory frameworks.

The analysis reveals both similarities and differences between the two jurisdictions. Common features include licensing procedures, training requirements, and mechanisms for oversight and sanctioning, while differences emerge in the scope of authority granted to private security personnel, the extent of state supervision, and the clarity of legal provisions. The findings suggest that, although both countries have established legal frameworks, there is scope for improvement. Further development of this sector requires not only the enhancement of regulatory solutions but, above all, their consistent implementation and strengthening of institutional oversight, which can increase the responsibility, efficiency, and contribution of private security to the wider national security system.

Keywords: *private security, private security officer, Republic of Serbia, Republic of North Macedonia, regulation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to financial limitations, technological developments, and responsibilities within the domain of national security, certain functions that were the exclusive prerogative of the state and its institutions have been assumed by private security entities.

The reasons for the justification of the existence and further development of the private security sector include good material and technical equipment, practical and financial relief for the police, economic benefits that strengthen the state budget and, finally, increasing the overall security of citizens and the state (Гергинова, 2016, pp. 386-387). Only with the emergence of structured entities whose operations are directly or indirectly aligned with the security functions of the state and within the framework of the national security system can private security be conceptualized and analyzed as a distinct field of activity (Marković, 2023; Marković, 2025).

This paper aims to provide a comparative analysis of the legal framework of private security in the Republic of Serbia and in the Republic of North Macedonia. The rationale for a comparative approach lies in the similarity of legal systems in the two jurisdictions, their shared regional context, and the alignment with broader European standards.

The study focuses on examining key normative aspects of private security regulation, including licensing requirements, professional qualifications and training standards, the scope of powers vested in private security officers, as well as mechanisms of state supervision and sanctioning. The paper seeks to identify similarities and differences between the two regulatory systems, and to highlight laws that explain why private security is important, how it protects people and property, how it should function within the security system, and that its goal is to provide quality and efficient services, not to be a mere formal obligation (Бакрески, 2016, pp. 185-186).

Structurally, the paper is organized into several sections: the first section outlines the theoretical and conceptual foundations of private security; the second section presents an overview of the legal framework of private security in the Republic of Serbia; the third section analyzes the regulatory framework in the Republic of North Macedonia; and the final section offers a comparative assessment and concluding observations.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF PRIVATE SECURITY

Private security is often considered through the concept of *policing*, whereby a distinction is made between public policing and private policing (Daničić and Stajić, 2008; Mijalković and Popović, 2015; Kesić, 2009). Research from the 1980s indicated the accelerated growth of private security and the redistribution of responsibility for protection from the public to the private sector (Cunningham and Taylor, 1985).

The boundary between public and private policing is increasingly blurred, as functions once reserved exclusively for the state have been delegated to private actors. Rather than a simple division of police work, this reflects a broader redistribution of security governance between public and private sectors (Shearing, 1992, p. 411). Despite differing institutional arrangements and responsibilities, these sectors operate in an interconnected manner within a unified security system (Stenning, 2009, p. 23).

In this context, private policing encompasses citizen policing, private security, and private investigative activities (Sparrow, 2014, p. 2), with private security representing the operational component of private policing (Davidović, 2011, p. 460).

The term *private security* refers to the full range of activities aimed at protecting property, individuals, and businesses, carried out by private legal entities engaged in the provision of security services. Comprehensively defined, private security is “a planned and organized independent or joint activity and function of individuals, organizations, private or professional agencies, aimed at their own protection or the protection of others, as well as

the protection of relevant persons, spaces, objects, businesses or activities, which are not covered by the exclusive protection of state authorities” (Daničić and Stajić, 2008, p. 14).

3. PRIVATE SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Although certain elements of private security existed within previous legal solutions, formal institutionalization was achieved only in 2013 with the adoption of the Law on Private Security and Law on Detective Activities (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, No. 104/2013). Since then, the legal framework has been amended twice and further elaborated through several bylaws.³⁵ However, the adoption of these laws continued to face problems such as the lack of adequately trained personnel, organizational difficulties, and the influence of political connections (Milošević, 2010, p. 123).

The Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia”, No. 104/2013, 42/2015 and 87/2018) defines private security as the provision of services that include the protection of persons, property, and business operations through physical and technical security measures, unless such activities fall within the exclusive competence of state authorities. It also includes the transport of cash and valuables, as well as the maintenance of order at public gatherings, which are carried out by licensed legal entities, entrepreneurs, or internal security units formed for their own needs (Art. 2).

Chapter II regulates the protection of mandatorily secured facilities (Art. 4-5). Chapter III specifies the types of services and licenses that can be obtained by registered legal entities and entrepreneurs for performing private security activities (Art.6-7).

Chapter IV establishes a comprehensive licensing system as a prerequisite for the lawful provision of private security services. The law provides for different types of licenses for legal persons and individuals, depending on the type of service (Art. 9 and 11), with clearly defined general and special conditions (Art. 10 and 12). Licenses and authorizations for training are issued by the Ministry of Internal Affairs (hereinafter: Ministry), and the law regulates in detail the procedures for issuance, extension, revocation and legal protection (Art. 13-18).

Chapter V regulates the way private security services are performed, based on the principle that these activities are carried out without encroaching on the competence of state authorities and with full respect for the rights and freedoms of citizens (Art. 19), exclusively based on a written contract with the service user (Art. 20). The law specifies the obligation of prior risk assessment and preparation of a security plan as basic documents for organizing physical and technical protection (Art. 20-21). The tasks of physical protection with and without weapons are specially regulated, as well as the powers and obligations of security officers (Art. 22-28). Provisions on technical protection (Art. 29-30) define the application of technical systems and measures in compliance with prescribed standards and privacy protection, while the transport of money and valuable shipments is governed by special security requirements (Art. 36-39). Chapter V also regulates the police service at public gatherings and sports events (Art. 40-43), the mandatory establishment and operation of

³⁵The currently valid bylaws (December, 2025) are: Regulation on minimum technical requirements for the mandatory installation of technical protection systems in banks and other financial organizations (“OG of RS”, No. 9/2021-18), Regulation on the method of performing technical protection tasks and using technical means (“OG of RS”, No. 91/2019-89), Regulation on the professional exam for performing private security and security guard services (“OG of RS”, No. 74/2019-55), Regulation on the method of exercising the powers of security officers (“OG of RS”, No. 59/2019-22), Regulation on the color and components of the security officer uniform (“OG of RS”, No. 49/2019-73), Regulation on programs and methods of performing professional training for performing private security and security guard services (“OG of RS”, No. 15/2019-58) and the Regulation on detailed conditions for issuing authorizations for conducting training for performing private security and security guard services (“OG of RS”, No. 15/2019-56).

control centers (Art. 44), as well as the self-protection activity of legal entities for their own needs (Art. 45).

Chapter VI defines the powers of private security officers, which are applied exclusively within the law, proportionally and in accordance with specific circumstances (Art. 46). All powers must be clearly defined in the contract with the service user, and their regulation ensures the legal, proportional and controlled work of private security officers.

Subsequent chapters contain detailed rules on uniforms, identification, vehicle marking, record keeping, data protection, supervision and sanctions. Officials must wear a uniform during work, which must be distinguished from the uniforms of state bodies (Art. 60-61), while identification is issued by the Ministry and must be worn visibly or shown at the request of authorized persons (Art. 62-64). Legal entities and entrepreneurs must keep extensive records (Art. 67-67a), and the collected data is confidential and used exclusively for the purpose for which it was collected (Art. 68-69). The Ministry and authorized police officers supervise the performance of work (Art. 70-75). Violations of the law are subject to fines and protective measures, including a ban on activities or business (Art. 76-84).

4. PRIVATE SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

The normative basis for the development of private security in the Republic of North Macedonia was established by the adoption of two laws in December 1999: the Law on the Security of Persons and Property and the Law on Detective Activities, published in the “Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia”, No. 80 of December 17, 1999. As in neighboring countries, individuals and groups who illegally protected property, maintained ties with political parties, or had ties with the police suspected of recruiting people continued to operate for some time (Dimovski, Ilijevski and Babanoski, 2012, p. 78).

The Law on the Security of Persons and Property was the first formal legal instrument to establish the basic criteria and conditions for the normative regulation of the new activity – the protection of persons and property. In addition to the normative regulation of basic issues, the aforementioned law enabled the establishment of the Chamber of the Republic of Macedonia for the Security of Persons and Property, as an expert body whose work contributed to the drafting of the text of the new draft of the Law on Private Security.

Thus, in 2012, the Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia”, No. 166/2012) was adopted. This law was the first to carry out a terminological adjustment of the name of the activity, changing it from *security of persons and property* to *private security*. Since then, the Law has been revised several times, including amendments in 2020, and several bylaws have been adopted.³⁶

The Law on Private Security (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia”, No. 166/2012, 164/2013, 148/2015, 193/2015, 55/2016; and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia”, No. 302/2020) defines private security as an activity of public interest,

³⁶ In 2014, the following bylaws were adopted: the Regulation on Amendments and Supplements to the Regulation on the Content of the Program and the Method of Training Persons for Physical and Technical Security, Taking Professional Exams, The Form and Content of the Application Form for Issuing a Private Security License and the Form and Content of the Private Security License Forms, and the Regulation on Criteria Regarding Spatial Conditions and Material, Technical and IT Equipment of the Premises for Taking Professional Exams for Physical and Technical Security (“OG of RM” No. 137/14), as well as the Regulation on the Method of Scoring Answers to Questions from Professional Exams for Physical and Technical Security (“OG of RM” No. 145/14).

which includes the protection of persons and property carried out by legal entities that have a private security license (Art. 2 and 7).

The types of private security are listed in two forms: providing services and for own needs (Art. 8). Private security in the form of providing services refers to the protection of persons and property based on a signed contract, performed by a legal entity that has registered its activity and obtained a license for private security in the form of providing services. Private security for own needs refers to the protection of property and persons within a legal entity, performed by private security workers employed by that entity, which has obtained a license for private security for its own needs (Art. 7).

Furthermore, the law distinguishes between physical security and technical security, with physical security including physical protection, monitoring and patrol security, security of transport and transfer of money and other valuables, and security of public gatherings and other events (Art. 9).

Chapter II systematically regulates the conditions for performing private security activities through a precisely defined regime of permits and licenses for legal persons and individuals. A legal person may perform private security activities only after obtaining a permit from the Ministry and registering the activity, fulfilling the prescribed conditions. The law also provides for the possibility of revoking the permit in case of inactivity or violation of regulations (Art. 10-19).

In parallel, individuals may perform private security activities only with the possession of a license and a private security identification card (legitimation), issued by the Chamber of the Republic of North Macedonia for private security (hereinafter: Chamber), under prescribed conditions (Art. 20-22). The system of training and professional examinations is regulated in detail, with the participation of the Chamber and institutional supervision by the Ministry (Art. 23-24-ж). Legitimation cards are issued and revoked depending on the continuous fulfillment of legal requirements (Art. 25).

Chapter III regulates physical security with weapons (Art. 27-31), physical protection (Art. 32), patrol and monitoring (Art. 33), the use of intervention patrols (Art. 34), as well as the provision of transport and transfer of money and valuables with specially equipped vehicles and trained workers (Art. 35-37).

Public security at events and public gatherings is regulated by Articles 38-39, including the obligation to develop a security plan for larger gatherings. Technical security is ensured by utilizing technical means to prevent unlawful actions and protect the privacy of citizens (Art. 40-41), with the obligation to maintain the quality and accuracy of devices in accordance with established standards (Art. 42).

Chapter IV covers the area of private security for own needs (Article 43), regulating the permit for the security of property and persons of a legal entity, which is performed by the employees of that entity, with a prohibition on providing services to other persons.

Chapter V covers the area of mandatory private security (Article 44) and regulates cases when the government prescribes mandatory security, as well as the possibility of providing security through its own employees or by engaging legal entities that provide security services.

Chapter VI regulates the powers of security officers (Art. 45). The security officer is obliged to carry identification (Art. 46), act on the orders of authorized officials (Art. 47), respect the reputation and dignity of citizens and human rights when exercising his powers (Art. 48), and prepare a written report for all actions (Art. 57).

Chapter VII regulates the uniforms and identification (Art. 58), while Chapter VIII regulates the powers and method of financing the Chamber.

The legislative framework of the Republic of North Macedonia establishes a high degree of formalization in the field of private security through detailed standardized records, supervision and misdemeanor liability. The Ministry maintains a central record of permits with long retention periods for personal data (Art. 62), while the Chamber and legal entities have statutory obligations to keep special records (Art. 63 and 64), with mandatory application of regulations on data protection (Art. 65).

Supervision is centralized in the Ministry (Art. 66-70). The misdemeanor system is elaborated and differentiated according to the types of subjects, with high fines and protective measures prohibiting the performance of activities (Art. 72-76-v). The normative framework is rounded off by the minister's broad authority to enact bylaws (Art. 79).

5. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PRIVATE SECURITY SYSTEM IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA AND THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

The definition of private security in the legislation of the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of North Macedonia indicates significant normative similarity in basic concepts, but also certain differences in terminological and structural approaches. The Law on Private Security of the Republic of Serbia (hereinafter: LoPSRS) defines private security as the activity of providing services for the protection of persons, property, and businesses, through physical and technical protection, when these activities are not within the exclusive jurisdiction of state authorities. It also includes the activities of transporting money, valuables and other consignments, maintaining order at public gatherings, sports events and other places of gathering (Art. 2 LoPSRS).

Similarly, the Law on Private Security of the Republic of North Macedonia (hereinafter: LoPSRNM) defines private security as the activity of protecting persons and property, which is carried out as a service or for one's own needs, while also clearly distinguishing it from activities that fall under the exclusive jurisdiction of state authorities (Art. 7, 8 and 9 LoPSRNM). The performance of activities in the form of providing services to others or for one's own needs is recognized in both legal solutions. However, Macedonian legislation places a more explicit emphasis on the distinction between contractual private security services and internal (self-protection) activities, while Serbian legislation integrates both forms within a single normative definition. On the other hand, the approach to defining private security in the Republic of Serbia is broader in terms of activities.

As subjects of private security, Serbian legislation recognizes a legal entity for private security, a private security entrepreneur, and a security officer (Art. 3 LoPSRS). Macedonian legislation, on the other hand, recognizes only two categories: a legal entity for private security and a private security worker (hereinafter: security officer) (Art. 3 and 7 LoPSRNM). However, it can be concluded that the first category in Macedonian law includes micro-traders, small traders, medium-sized traders and large traders (see more in the section on penal provisions in LoPSRNM).

In terms of types of work, Serbian law explicitly differentiates between risk assessment, physical and technical protection of persons and property, supervision and maintenance of technical protection systems, as well as securing the transport of money and valuables outside the jurisdiction of the Ministry (Art. 6 LoPSRS), which it further specifies through a licensing system. By contrast, Macedonian law systematizes private security work primarily through the division into physical and technical security, with physical security further broken down into physical protection, monitoring and patrol, securing the transport and transfer of money and other valuables, as well as securing public gatherings and other

events (Art. 9 LoPSRNM). This difference indicates a more detailed approach of the Serbian legislator in terms of types of services, in contrast to the Macedonian normative model that relies on broader, functionally defined categories.

In terms of licensing, Serbian law establishes a differentiated and functionally specific system, with clearly separated types of licenses for specific activities (Art. 8-12 LoPSRS), with clearly prescribed general and special conditions, the time validity of licenses, and the reasons for their revocation (Art. 16-17 LoPSRS). In North Macedonia, the regulation is normatively simpler and more focused on licensing the activity as a whole (see more in Articles 12-14 LoPSRNM).

In North Macedonia, the right of a legal entity to provide private security is conditional on registering the activity and obtaining a permit from the Ministry, either for the provision of services or for its own needs (Art. 10 and 12 LoPSRNM). This corresponds to the solution in Serbia, where the performance of the activity is also conditional on a license from the competent authority and registration in the register (Art. 9 and 10 LoPSRS). When it comes to the conditions for issuing a permit to legal entities, Serbian law contains fewer quantitatively specified criteria, relying more on secondary legislation (Art. 13 LoPSRS).

Differences are observed in the time period for notifying the competent entities about the cessation of work (eight days in Serbia and three days in North Macedonia); in the competent entity itself (the competent police administration in Serbia and the Chamber in North Macedonia) and in the obligation to start work within six months from the date of issuance of the license (Art. 11 LoPSRNM). Also, in North Macedonia, the Chamber of Private Security has a significant role in the licensing system (Chapter VIII). In contrast, Serbian legislation does not foresee the existence of such a body, but rather allows for the establishment of an advisory body to monitor the field of private security and improve cooperation, with the Minister responsible for establishing the Expert Council for the Improvement of Private Security and Public-Private Partnership in the Security Sector (Art. 75). Furthermore, the latest amendments to Serbian legislation provide for the possibility of engaging an accredited body that assesses the compliance of the quality of private security services (Art. 75a LoPSRS).

In relation to individuals, both systems provide for the mandatory possession of a license and identification as a basic prerequisite for work (Art. 12 and 63 LoPSRS; Art. 20 and 25 LoPSRNM), with almost identical conditions (Art. 12 LoPSRS; Art. 22 LoPSRNM). However, Macedonian law stands out with an elaborate and transparent system of training and professional examinations, with electronic testing and supervision (Art. 24-24-ж LoPSRNM), while in Serbia, this segment is regulated more concisely, with greater dependence on bylaws. Both legal systems require mandatory training and the successful completion of a professional exam; however, in Serbia, these activities are supervised primarily by state authorities, whereas in North Macedonia, the Chamber of Private Security performs most functions related to quality control and professional standards.

When comparing the regulation of private security services in Serbia and North Macedonia, it is evident that both legal systems are based on the common principle that private security services must be performed lawfully, without violating public order and without encroaching on the jurisdiction of state authorities (Art. 19 LoPSRS and Art. 5 LoPSRNM), and with the obligation to conclude a contract for the provision of services (Art. 20 LoPSRS and Art. 6 LoPSRNM). In Serbia, Chapter V of the Law on Private Security establishes a highly detailed and procedurally elaborated framework that includes the obligation to prepare a risk assessment and a security plan (Art. 20 LoPSRS), as well as elaborated private security services (Art. 21-45 LoPSRS). In North Macedonia, Chapter III

of the Law on Private Security regulates the manner of performing private security at a more general normative level (Art. 27-42 LoPSRNM), with an emphasis on the security plan when a public gathering or event is held (Art. 39 LoPSRNM).

In terms of the powers of security officers, the regulations are basically the same, and the powers are equivalent. What is noticeable is that the powers are more comprehensively prescribed by both law and bylaws in Serbian legislation. For example, Macedonian legislation only distinguishes the use of weapons and the use of trained dogs from means of coercion (Art. 55 and 56 LoPSRNM). Moreover, in both systems, the identification of officers, notification and reporting, as well as the obligation to respect human dignity and the proportional use of force, constitute a common normative foundation.

Both legal systems prescribe the obligation to keep registers. In Serbian legislation, this obligation belongs to the legal entity for private security, the private security entrepreneur, and educational institutions authorized to conduct training (Articles 67 and 67a LoPSRS). In Macedonian legislation, this obligation belongs to the Ministry, the Chamber, and legal entities that provide private security (Articles 62, 63 and 64 LoPSRNM). There are differences in terms of prescribing the contents of the register, which are more detailed in Serbia, as well as the obligation to maintain them. In Serbia, the legislator refers to the legal retention period, while in North Macedonia, the period is precisely expressed in years.

Both legal systems prescribe the obligation to supervise the work of private security entities. In Serbian legislation, supervision is carried out by the Ministry, authorized police officers, and inspection bodies (Art. 70 and 71 LoPSRS). In Macedonian legislation, supervision is carried out by the Ministry through authorized police officers and the supervisory commission formed by the Ministry (Art. 66 and 67 LoPSRNM). Both legislations prescribe the powers of authorized police officers, with the provision that in Serbian legislation, some powers are prescribed in more detail (see, for example, Art. 71, par. 7 and Art. 73 LoPSRS).

In terms of penal provisions, both legal solutions have their own specificities. In Serbia, penal provisions are differentiated in relation to legal entities and private security entrepreneurs, responsible persons and private security officers, as well as legal entities that use private security services and responsible persons in them, organizers of gatherings, legal entities that carry out self-protection activities, and educational institutions that conduct training, including responsible persons and lecturers (Chapter XI LoPSRS). In North Macedonia, penal provisions are differentiated in relation to legal entities for private security and responsible persons in them, for individuals, (i.e. security officers), but also for the Chamber and for authorized police officers of the Ministry (Chapter XI LoPSRNM), which is not recognized in Serbian legislation.

Finally, both legal solutions single out a special type of facilities whose protection and security are mandatory. These are mandatorily secured objects (Art. 4-5 LoPSRS) or special objects of importance for security (Art. 44 LoPSRNM).

Analyzing the texts of the laws, it is noticeable that certain issues are elaborated to varying extents, and that issues less elaborated in the law are elaborated in bylaws. If we take the authorization of security officers as an example, Serbian legislation has elaborated this area in a separate bylaw, while in Macedonian legislation, this has been done in the law itself. Although in both cases the laws are supplemented by bylaws, a greater degree of normative detail and greater standardization is noticeable in Serbia.

6. CONCLUSION

A comparative analysis shows that the regulation of private security in the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of North Macedonia rests on a common conceptual basis. Both legal frameworks show significant normative convergence in defining private security, regulating licensing, prescribing conditions for legal and natural persons, establishing oversight mechanisms, and protecting human rights through the principles of legality, proportionality and accountability. However, significant differences still exist in legislative technique and regulatory intensity. Serbian legislation is characterized by a more detailed, functionally differentiated and risk-oriented normative model, with extensive procedural regulation, a segmented licensing system, elaborate registers, supervision and penal provisions, and a stronger emphasis on direct state control. In contrast, Macedonian legislation adopts a more simplified approach, relying on broader legal categories, simplified licensing of activities, and a pronounced role for the Chamber of Private Security as a mechanism of professional self-regulation under state supervision.

Despite the formal normative regulation of the private security system in the Republic of Serbia and the Republic of North Macedonia, practice shows that the established legal frameworks still do not guarantee full professionalization. The problems that once existed in the form of a large number of retired or dismissed former members of the security services, connections with political parties, and even inadequately trained personnel and insufficient material and technical equipment are still present to some extent. Inconsistent application of regulations, limited capacities of supervisory bodies, and existing political and market pressures contribute to the survival of unfair competition and uneven quality of security services. In this context, private security has not yet been fully accepted as a strategically regulated part of the national security system. Further development of this sector requires not only the improvement of regulatory solutions but, above all, their consistent implementation and strengthening of institutional oversight.

The analysis carried out in the paper includes only the parent laws in the field of private security – the Law on Private Security of the Republic of Serbia and the Law on Private Security of the Republic of North Macedonia. Future research may be more comprehensive, encompassing a broader normative framework that includes documents such as the constitution, strategic documents, relevant laws and bylaws, as well as the rules of the profession and “good practice”

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